

Ultra-violet Absorption in the Mixtures of Chromates and Dichromates.

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Some results on the extinction coefficients of the mixtures of chromates and dichromates have recently been reported and the data have been utilised to determine the percentage composition of such mixtures (Paranjpe and Tawde, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1929-30, 6, 533). The above procedure is applicable only to concentrated solutions, as no absorption in the visible region is given by weak solutions of these mixtures.

Selective absorption is given by these solutions in the ultra-violet region. Hantzsch, (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1910 72, 362) formulated definite absorption curve for dichromate and chromate. The peak of the chromate curve lies in the same wave-length region as that of dichromate. This holds also for the minima of the curves. There is one band in the solution of dichromate and two bands in that of chromate. As chromate is changed gradually into dichromate by the addition of acid, its second band begins to disappear. This observation has been utilised to obtain a quantitative estimate of the percentage composition of the mixture.

EXPERIMENTAL.

For these experiments, a solution of a single salt or of two salts will be called normal when it contains one gram-atom (52 g.) of chromium in a litre of solution.

The spectrograph used was R. Fuess quartz prism instrument recording a region from 5200 Å to 2100 Å. The source of light used was an iron arc. The main difficulty is that the feeble lines disappear altogether, while the stronger ones persist through the band. In such cases the observations were confirmed by using a carbon arc.

The experiments were made under uniform conditions at room temperature.

Results.

The peak (transmission band) of both chromate and dichromate and their mixtures was found to be at 3140\AA . The dispersion of the spectrograph in this region was 14\AA per mm. By trial photographs the thickness and concentration of solution in Baly's tube were so adjusted that the layer just began to absorb light in this wavelength. This thickness when reduced to \bar{N} -10,000 basis for any solution represents the height of its transmission peak. The results are given in figures 1 and 2 below.

Fig. 1.

The percentage compositions of mixtures of chromate and dichromate as estimated by the above curves were compared as in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*) with the values obtained by the chemical method (Sacher, *Farbenzeit*, 1916, 22, 213). The agreement is fairly satisfactory and similar to that reported previously.

Fig. 2.

Summary.

The estimation of chromate in presence of dichromate reported in a previous paper, has been extended to more dilute solutions.

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